

MAPPA: MONITORING AND ANALYSIS OF PLASTIC POLLUTION IN AQUATIC ENVIRONMENTS

Protocol for water samples processing for microplastics analysis

Ver. 1.2

1. Objective:

Obtaining potential plastic particles $> 20 \mu\text{m}$ (microplastics; MPs) in glass fiber filters (GF/C) for characterization (shape, color, size) and subsequent analysis of their polymer composition.

2. To be considered:

- **Inspect** each GF/C filter under the microscope before use. It is common to find plastic particles or microfibers from the manufacturing process.
- **Filter** all reagents before use.
- **Evaluate and record** potential sources of MPs contamination in your laboratory.
- **Clean** all work surfaces with ethanol 70% before working.
- **Always wear** cotton lab coats and gloves.
- If possible, **avoid or restrict** the presence of people in the laboratory while handling the sample.
- Perform at least one negative/blank sample **ddmmyyy Blanco_1** following the same procedure used for water samples (milli Q water filtered on the study site and processed in the laboratory)
- Expose a filter (**Blanco_2 ddmmyyy**) in a petri dish in the laboratory during sample processing to detect any airborne particle contamination.

Scheme for sample processing

Please, send an email to alfonsomb@riam.kyushu-u.ac.jp before processing/sending the samples.

3. Sample Processing:

3.1. Materials

Equipment:

- Fume hood
- Laminar flow (recommended)
- Vacuum pump
- Hot plate, water bath, or incubator
- Scale
- Trinocular stereomicroscope with camera (photos)
- Image J software (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/download.html>): Pre-calibrate according to your microscope

Laboratory instruments:

- Glass or metal filter equipment Ø 47 mm
- Washing bottles (2)
- Petri dishes Ø 50/90 mm
- Glass bottles for reagents
- Bottle for chemical waste
- Tweezers (fine tip)
- Beakers (many, 500 mL, 250 mL)
- Nylon mesh 25 cm² (smaller mesh size than the one used in the survey)
- Glass funnel Ø ~12 cm
- Metal Clips (2)

Chemical Regents & Consumables:

- Filters Ø 47 mm: optional glass fiber (GF/C) 1.2 µm; Nitrocellulose or cellulose 8 µm, or polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) 5 µm
- Glass slides
- Aluminum foil
- Nitrile or latex gloves
- Milli Q Water or Distilled Water
- Hydrogen peroxide H₂O₂ 30%
- NaCl (lab grade)
- Ethanol 70%
- Double-sided tape (any brand)
- Eppendorf tubes (2 or 5 mL)

3.2. Pre-filtering

⚠ Caution: To avoid sample contamination, wear a lab coat and gloves. When handling the sample, open it inside a laminar flow cabinet or fume hood.

Note: If the sample contains too much natural debris, plankton, etc., work in several steps to prevent the sample from overflowing into the funnel.

- a) Carefully open the sample under the laminar flow hood (turned on), or if unavailable, you may do so in a fume hood (turned off) to minimize contamination through exposure.
- b) If there is organic material such as leaves, wood residues, algae, which are not of interest, remove them using tweezers, rinsing them three times to avoid losing any plastic particles or adhered fibers.
- c) Filter the sample using a glass funnel and a nylon mesh filter, as shown in Fig. 1, folding the mesh with the help of metal clips to secure it. Another option is to use a stainless-steel sieve with a mesh opening smaller than that of your sampling net.
- d) Rinse the inside of the sample container several times with Milli-Q or filtered distilled water using a wash bottle and pour the liquid into the nylon funnel along with the rest of the sample.
- e) Pour the retained material into a labeled beaker, rinsing it with Milli-Q water until no material remains on the nylon mesh/sieve. Visually inspect the mesh under the stereomicroscope for any attached particles.

Figure 1. Nylon mesh. Funnel for filtering. Correct position for use of laminar flow cabinet.

If you **don't have experience with MPs analysis**, keep the sample **refrigerated** (4 °C). Contact us by email to coordinate sample shipment.

3.3. Digestion

⚠ **Caution:** Perform this process inside a fume hood to remove H₂O₂ vapors. Wear protective gear, including gloves and lab coats, to prevent burns.

- Filter a 30% H₂O₂ solution with a GF/C filter (Ø 47) and filter equipment.
- Add H₂O₂ to the beaker until the sample is submerged.
- Place the beaker on a heating plate or water bath at < 50 °C.
- Cover the sample with aluminum foil. Check the temperature regularly. It is important that it does not exceed the desired temperature to prevent the degradation of the particles.
- As the liquid evaporates, add more H₂O₂ as needed until all organic impurities are eliminated (or reduced to a negligible level). Let cool to room temperature.

When finish, there are **two options**:

- No residue is left of any kind:** Filter the sample with filtering equipment and GF/C filters under the laminar flow cabinet (Correct use: 25 cm opening). Use multiple filters as needed, ensuring that a sample film does not form, thereby preventing the entrapment of certain particles underneath. Place each filter on a glass Petri dish and label (Figure 2).
NOTE: Avoid applying excessive vacuum pressure to prevent the fragmentation of weathered particles.

Figure 2. Filtering equipment. Sample after digestion with hydrogen peroxide.

Example of a sample in GF/C filter.

- There are residues of inorganic origin (sand or others):** Extract the H₂O₂ solution by filtration with a nylon mesh or metal sieve (Ø pore < net) under a laminar flow cabinet (Correct use: 25 cm opening). Rinse the sample with a washing bottle with Milli Q or filtered distilled water, and then wash the sample back into the beaker using more water. Proceed to step **3.4**.

3.4. Density Separation

⚠ Caution: Whenever possible, perform this process inside a laminar flow hood (Correct usage: 25 cm opening) to prevent sample contamination. In the absence of one, you may conduct the procedure in a turned-off fume hood to reduce air circulation and potential contamination through deposition.

Note: If the sample contains too much inorganic waste after digestion, work in several steps to prevent the sample from overflowing into the funnel.

- Prepare a NaCl solution with 29.2 g in 100 mL of distilled water ($5M = 1.19 \text{ g/cm}^3$); Filter the NaCl solution using a GF/C filter or similar ($\varnothing 47$).
- Add 100 mL of saturated salt solution to the sample beaker.
- Mix for 10 minutes and let it settle for one hour. This step can be done in a separating funnel or directly in the beaker with the sample (Fig. 3).
- Collect the supernatant with the floating particles ($1/3$ of the liquid) with a glass pipette. You can also use tweezers for larger particles. Place in a new beaker*.
- With the remaining liquid ($2/3$), repeat steps b, c, and d three times, and place the supernatant in the same beaker*.
- Filter the supernatant liquid resulting from the three extractions using filter equipment and a GF/C filter $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ inside a laminar or extraction flow cabinet (Correct use: 25 cm opening).

Use as many filters as necessary, preventing a thick layer of sample from forming on top of it. Place the filter(s) in labeled petri dishes and allow to dry at room temperature or in an oven at a moderate temperature ($40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 3. Example of density separation. Left: decantation funnel. Right: beaker separation.

3.5. Counting and characterization under the microscope

⚠ Caution: It is important to emphasize that there is always a subjective element during visual identification; therefore, the examiner must have good practical training.

- Inspect the filter for potential plastic particles under a stereomicroscope following a pattern like the one shown in the right figure.
- Take a picture of each particle you find.
- Describe it according to its shape (**3.5.1**) and color (**3.5.3**)
- Measure its size, according to **section 3.5.2**, using the free software Image J. Always **calibrate** according to the magnification used before measuring.

Classification criteria:

For a more detailed description, we recommend referring to the guideline in Lusher et al., (2020)

3.5.1. Shape

Bead (BD; pellets, grains, spheres, microbeads): These are specialized plastic particles crafted to be small in size, typically within the microplastic range. They may take the form of spheres or granules and exhibit a smooth surface without any indications of fragmentation from larger sources. Designed with precision, they display deliberate shaping and consistent sizing characteristics (Lusher et al., 2020).

Fibers (FBs): Described as filaments or lines, fibers frequently constitute the predominant fraction of particles found in environmental samples. These fibers are distinguished by their length, which exceeds their width by a significant margin. Typically, their widths measure less than 50-75 μm , commonly falling within the range of 10-30 μm , while their lengths can extend from several millimeters to centimeters. Plastic fibers typically feature a smooth surface, although certain textile manufacturing processes can induce the formation of smaller fibers on their surfaces, known as fibrils, resulting in a less uniform structure (Lusher et al., 2020).

Note: Fibers may also be found in bundles or assemblies, wherein several fibers are tightly wound together in a knot-like formation. It is advisable to separate and count bundles of fibers as individual fibers whenever feasible, particularly when the bundles contain fibers with distinct appearances. This ensures accurate characterization and assessment, particularly in cases where different types of fibers are present within the same bundle.

Film (FI): Described as fragmented materials, these particles typically possess two dimensions that are notably larger than the third, with the latter sometimes measuring only a few micrometers. They are often characterized as more flexible compared to fragments, capable of bending or wrinkling while maintaining a degree of resistance to breakage. However, it's worth noting that polymer-based paints, despite their flexibility, can exhibit relative brittleness (Lusher et al., 2020).

Fragment (FR): Primarily originating from the degradation of larger materials and the breakdown of larger plastics, these particles constitute a diverse category, including subcategories such as foam. Fragments can be distinguished from beads by their relative angularity. They may exhibit smooth or angular edges, appearing flat or irregular, often suggesting detachment from a larger piece of material (Lusher et al., 2020).

Foam (FO; Foams): Foams are fragments of materials that incorporate a foaming agent during the setting process, examples of which include expanded polystyrene (EPS), expanded polyvinyl chloride (EPVC), and similar materials. When subjected to physical handling, foams can be crushed, yet they possess the ability to regain their original shape (Lusher et al., 2020).

Size

The maximum Feret diameter (Figure at right) has been suggested as the most appropriate measurement, as it refers to the length of the longest line joining two points on the contour of an object (GESAMP, 2019).

- **Macro:** 1000-25mm
- **Meso:** 25-1 mm
- **Micro:** < 1mm -1 μ m
- **Nano:** < 1 μ m

3.5.2. Colour

It is suggested that the homogeneous color indicates plastic particles, particularly fragments. Despite this, it is important to note that there are exceptions, especially in the case of particles that are composed of multiple-colored sections or as a result of the digestion protocol (Lusher et al., 2020).

To reduce bias among researchers, it is recommended to record colors at the level of secondary colors: **red, orange, yellow, green, blue, and violet, in addition to including black, white, and transparent.**

3.6. Particle selection for further polymer analysis

This section is for those who will send the samples for polymer analysis (see initial schematic). Those who rely on their **laboratory/colleagues** to analyze the samples follow their usual agreed protocol (filter, FTIR, Raman, etc.)

- a) Select several **random particles** that represent **20%** of the total abundance of the sample. If the number of particles is less than 30, send all the particles.
- b) For those particles that are easily visible > 1 mm, take a photo and place them in a labeled Eppendorf (2-5 mL). You can only put more than one particle if they are easily distinguishable (color, shape).
- c) For particles < 1 mm, place them one by one on a slide with double-sided tape. Do this gently and prevent the particle from submerging completely in the glue. It is important that a surface is exposed for further analysis. Try to leave a significant distance between different particles, number them, and circle them using an indelible marker. Divide the surface of the tape into numbered sections for easy identification (Fig. 4).

Example for reference: Section 1, particle No. 3

- d) Check the magnifying glass to ensure **no additional particles/fibers** are stuck to the tape to avoid confusion. Store the slide in an individually labeled petri dish. Tape the slide to the surface of the petri dish to prevent movement during transport (A plastic petri dish can be used for this purpose to reduce the risk of breakage during shipping).

Figure 4. Magnified view of particles on a double-sided tape. Example of double-sided tape slides in a petri dish for shipping.

References

GESAMP (2019) Guidelines for the monitoring and assessment of plastic litter and microplastics in the ocean (eds Kershaw P.J., Turra A. and Galgani F.), London, UK, GESAMP Joint Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection, 130pp. (GESAMP Reports and Studies, No. 99). DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-435>

Lusher, A. L., Bråte, I. L. N., Munno, K., Hurley, R. R., & Welden, N. A. (2020). Is it or isn't it: the importance of visual classification in microplastic characterization. *Applied spectroscopy*, 74(9), 1139-1153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00037028209307>